

Article

Evaluating Supply Chain Network Models for Third Party Logistics Operated Supply-Processing-Distribution in Thai Hospitals: An AHP-Fuzzy TOPSIS Approach

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Abstract: *Background:* This study introduces a novel supply chain management (SCM) model tailored for the hospital industry in Thailand. The model emphasises the integration of third-party logistics (3PL) providers to streamline supply-processing-distribution (SPD) functions. By outsourcing non-core activities like SPD to 3PL providers, hospitals can enhance their operational efficiency, allowing healthcare professionals to focus on core tasks and ultimately improving service delivery. *Methods:* This research employed a dual methodology, combining an analytic hierarchy process (AHP) with a Fuzzy Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (Fuzzy TOPSIS). These approaches evaluated various SCM models based on multiple hospital logistics performance attributes. *Results:* The AHP results highlighted on-time delivery, patient safety, utilisation rate, and emergency procurement as critical criteria for selecting the optimal model. Fuzzy TOPSIS analysis identified the SCIII: W-G-H model as the most suitable for implementation in Thai hospitals. This model incorporates a centralised warehouse for negotiation leverage, a Group Purchasing Organisation (GPO) for cost efficiency, and regional SPD hubs for effective inventory management and rapid responses to demand fluctuations or emergencies. *Conclusions:* Adopting this SCM model is expected to significantly enhance supply chain performance, reduce operational costs, and improve the quality and safety of patient care in Thai hospitals.

Keywords: hospital supply chain; supply chain management; supply-processing-distribution; 3PL; logistics; AHP; Fuzzy TOPSIS; Thailand

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1. Introduction

In Thailand, the increasing demand for health services has led to a high volume of complex hospital supplies management, including medical devices, medical supplies, and pharmaceutical products. This presents significant challenges for healthcare professionals, who must efficiently manage these supplies to ensure quality service and client satisfaction. Ineffective management can ultimately impact patient safety and satisfaction levels among hospital clients, including physicians, nurses, and pharmacists.

In response to these challenges, hospitals are encouraged to adapt by focusing on their core competencies and outsourcing non-core functions to third-party logistics providers (3PLs) [1]. According to Lieb and Kendrick [2], 3PLs are “external companies that handle logistics functions traditionally performed within an organisation”. Extensive research has highlighted the diverse range of services that 3PLs provide across various supply chains,

demonstrating their capability to provide comprehensive logistics solutions [2–4]. By leveraging 3PLs to manage non-healthcare processes, hospitals can enhance their operational capabilities, allowing healthcare professionals to concentrate on core healthcare functions and deliver services with a stronger emphasis on patient safety [1,5].

The supply processing distribution (SPD) logistics management model is proposed to improve hospital supply chains by involving a 3PL provider in operating these functions within a hospital setting. This model is recognised for its flexibility and adaptability and is often implemented as an in-house function [6,7]. It covers a wide range of logistics activities, including procurement, inventory management, and distribution, which has been shown to reduce costs and enhance hospital efficiency [8–11].

In Thailand, the largest private hospital group has engaged a 3PL provider to oversee the SPD functions. This provider is responsible for managing the inventory of medications and medical supplies across multiple hospitals within the group [12]. Despite their logistical expertise, the 3PL provider faces challenges due to the fragmented nature of logistics activities across different hospital sites [13,14]. This fragmentation has led to inefficiencies, particularly in cost management and responsiveness to demand [5,12,13].

To address these challenges, this research investigated optimal SPD supply chain management models operated by 3PL providers for implementation in Thai hospitals. The objective was to enable 3PL providers to efficiently manage non-healthcare processes, leveraging their logistical expertise, while allowing hospitals to concentrate on core healthcare functions with a focus on patient safety and responsiveness [8,11,12].

This study explored innovative SCM models that integrate SPD functions, aiming to find a feasible solution for real-world applications in the hospital setting in Thailand. Various SCM models incorporating SPD functions were proposed as alternatives for consideration. Furthermore, performance attributes related to SPD operations—such as supply management, inventory management, and distribution management—were identified. These attributes serve as key criteria for evaluating and selecting the most optimal model, which will also be used to establish theoretical hospital logistics performance criteria.

For selecting the most suitable SPD supply chain management model from among various proposed alternatives while considering multiple hospital logistics performance attributes, this study framed the issue as a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem. This research introduced an evaluation process using MCDM methods, which are frequently applied to solve supply chain management challenges. These methods range from singular approaches, such as the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) [15–18], to integrated or mixed models among AHP, analytic network process (ANP), TOPSIS, and Fuzzy TOPSIS [19–27].

In this study, AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS were employed as they are widely recognised for their effectiveness in handling MCDM problems. AHP is particularly useful for assigning priority weights to performance attributes, while Fuzzy TOPSIS addresses uncertainties in human preferences by converting them into scores. This approach is especially helpful when dealing with multiple criteria in supply chain management model evaluations, as it minimises inconsistencies in decision-making [21,23].

Consequently, this research developed a three-stage methodology integrating MCDM approaches into evaluated 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models. In the first stage, feasible supply chain management models were identified, and relevant hospital logistics performance attributes were determined through a review of literature and interviews with hospital supply chain experts. In the second stage, AHP was applied to assign weights and prioritise sub-criteria and criteria for hospital logistics performance attributes. Finally, Fuzzy TOPSIS was used to evaluate the alternatives and determine the most optimal SPD supply chain management model for practical implementation in Thai hospitals.

This paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive literature review. Section 3 describes the methodology used in the study. Section 4 proposes feasible alternatives for the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model in a hospital context. Section 5 evaluates the proposed supply chain management model alternatives

using crucial hospital logistics performance attributes as criteria and prioritises them using an integrated MCDM approach. Section 6 provides a detailed discussion of the findings, including practical implications for hospitals. Finally, Section 7 concludes the paper with a summary of the research contributions, limitations, and suggestions for future studies.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Supply Processing Distribution (SPD) Supply Chain Management Model

The supply processing distribution (SPD) model is a logistics management framework recommended for transforming traditional hospital supply chain practices [8,9,28]. This model focuses on managing medical consumables throughout the entire hospital supply chain, connecting key stakeholders from both internal and external chains. The primary objective of the SPD model is to improve supply chain management efficiency, allowing healthcare professionals to focus more on patient care. Researchers have proposed integrating the SPD model into hospital supply chain management to enhance the distribution and management of pharmaceuticals and medical consumables [28].

Recent research has explored the implementation of the SPD model in hospital supply chains. For instance, in China, integrating the SPD model with a supply-procurement platform and a lean logistics management system has enabled effective management of medical consumables within hospitals [8]. Additionally, there have been recommendations for optimising the logistics distribution network of the SPD model specifically for managing medical consumables in hospital environments [9,28,29]. In Japan, Tokyo University Hospital has outsourced its material management activities, utilising the SPD model for daily procurement, receiving, stocking, and replenishment of medical supplies, serums, and pharmaceutical items [30]. These studies underscore the growing interest in and application of the SPD model in hospital supply chain management, aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of healthcare services delivery.

In general, the SPD model consists of three primary functions: supply management (S), processing management (P), and distribution management (D). These functions are integrated to optimise hospital logistics management and improve the utilisation of medical supply chain resources. The physical characteristics of the SPD model include:

The first function, supply management (S), involves several key procedures that streamline the procurement and availability of medical consumables and hospital supplies. These procedures include establishing efficient supply-procurement platforms, classifying items based on purchasing categories, and integrating suppliers into the system. Key features include:

- Online supply-procurement platforms: These platforms enable real-time processing of transactions, providing visibility into item availability, status, and fund flow, improving procurement speed and transparency.
- Classification of items based on the Kraljic portfolio purchasing model: This model categorises items into four types—strategic, leverage, bottleneck, and non-critical—based on their supply risk and profit impact. Such classification allows for differentiated purchasing strategies, optimising procurement based on the nature of the item.
- Supplier integration and centralised procurement: By centralising procurement and integrating suppliers into the hospital's supply chain, workload is reduced, price advantages can be negotiated, and the supply of goods is stabilised to meet demand efficiently.
- Supplier evaluation: Suppliers are assessed using criteria such as delivery timeliness, product quality, availability, ease of selection, and potential for long-term partnerships. This evaluation process enhances the efficiency of procurement, helping hospitals maintain a reliable and high-quality supply chain.

The subsequent element, processing management (P), encompasses four fundamental procedures. Firstly, it necessitates the establishment of a central warehouse that functions as a hub for short-term storage and various processing activities, including inspection, storage, and repacking. Furthermore, it entails the development of two distinct packaging

types tailored to departmental consumption patterns: Amount-Based Packages (ABP) designed for standard departments and Procedure-Based Packages (PBP) intended for specific departments with unique operational requirements. Both packaging types are equipped with barcode labels for scanning, which facilitates real-time updates on status and consumption tracking. This information is subsequently employed to initiate settlements between the organisation and its suppliers, as well as to implement inventory control systems that include demand forecasting and analysis of efficiency-related factors. These systems empower the logistics department to ascertain safety stock levels, reorder points, order quantities, and order cycles, thereby optimising stock levels and enhancing overall inventory management.

Distribution management (D) is tasked with executing precise and timely processes to ensure safety during medical activities, utilising technologies for effective handling. By employing a logistics management platform and barcode technology, the organisation can monitor stock consumption, track inventory status, and manage inventory across all levels. Additionally, the consumption data derived from this system analysis informs the generation and distribution of ABPs and PBPs, ensuring their timely and appropriate allocation in terms of quantity to individual points of use.

The structure of the SPD supply chain management model is illustrated in Figure 1. This study aimed to develop a hospital supply chain management solution by integrating the SPD functions operated by a 3PL provider. Additionally, the investigation encompasses the identification of non-hospital key stakeholders and the design of a supply chain flow structure that is feasible and suitable for implementation in the context of Thai hospitals.

Figure 1. The structure of the SPD supply chain management model. Source: adapted from Liu et al. [8] and Senarak and Kritchanchai [12].

2.2. Current Implementation of the SPD Supply Chain Management Model in Thai Hospitals and Associated Challenges

In Thailand, the SPD model has been initially implemented in a large private hospital group, recognised as the largest and most well-known hospital group in Thailand and the Asia–Pacific region. This group ranks among the top five private hospital groups globally and currently consists of 48 hospitals with over 8000 beds across Thailand and other countries. Each hospital within the group is independently managed by its hospital director. The SPD functions for managing medical consumable supplies are separately operated by a 3PL provider at each hospital. Each hospital has a dedicated 3PL-SPD unit that serves as an inventory management unit located within its hospital warehouse.

The 3PL-SPD units at hospitals nationwide are tasked with managing inventory at each point of use and sending requisitions to the central head office of the 3PL-operated

SPD provider in Bangkok, Thailand, when stock replenishment is necessary. The order requisitions for medical consumable supplies from all hospitals within the group are then forwarded to suppliers or distributors. Subsequently, suppliers or distributors prepare and ship orders directly to each hospital's central warehouse. The 3PL-SPD unit at the hospital central warehouse distributes the supplies to the points of use based on actual consumption levels, ensuring optimal inventory levels are maintained. Finally, the hospitals process payments to suppliers separately, corresponding to the quantity of goods received within the specified timeframe.

The existing structure of the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model implemented in Thai hospitals is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The existing structure of the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model implemented in Thai hospitals.

Based on the existing practices observed in the hospital group in Thailand, the 3PL provider operating the SPD functions faces two primary challenges. First, there are inefficiencies in management, characterised by low inventory turnover, expiration of certain items, delayed emergency responses, and inadequate support for demand fluctuations. Furthermore, the lack of standardisation among various items contributes to confusion and administrative complexities, resulting in increased costs. Second, there is a deficiency in negotiation power regarding pricing, order quantities, and product returns.

Consequently, this study proposes innovative supply chain management models for 3PLs involved in SPD operations within hospitals and aims to identify the most suitable model for implementation in Thailand's hospital supply chains. This initiative seeks to improve the performance attributes of supply chain management in healthcare settings.

2.3. Application of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) in Supply Chain Management

The evaluation of a 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model that is most suitable for practical implementation in the context of Thai hospitals is framed as a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem. Accordingly, this research employs an integrated MCDM approach. MCDM techniques are widely used to assess multiple alternatives and select the most optimal solution [25,27]. These techniques offer a structured and comprehensive framework for evaluating and prioritising available alternatives based on various selection criteria, effectively incorporating the preferences and interests of diverse stakeholders into both quantitative and qualitative evaluations [25].

MCDM encompasses a range of techniques, each possessing distinct characteristics, and no single method is universally superior to the others [25,26]. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of MCDM in enhancing efficiency and competitiveness within supply chain management across various industries. For instance, Kritchanchai et al. [18] employed the AHP to select a product champion for the passenger car tire industry in Thailand, proposing a promotional strategy to boost competitiveness along the industrial value chain. Vijayakumar et al. [31] assessed project investment alternatives using a hybrid MDCM approach that combined Fuzzy AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS. Additionally, Hanine et al. [32] and Boonsothonsatit et al. [27] utilised AHP and TOPSIS for selecting suitable product technology systems for implementation in enterprises. Similarly, the selection of mobile health applications was conducted using AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS [23]. Their findings indicated that combining these methods effectively ensures the selection of technologies that align with an enterprise's capabilities and environment.

Other studies related to logistics and supply chain management have also utilised various MCDM techniques, such as Fuzzy AHP and PROMETHEE II for agri-food supplier selection [26], Fuzzy Delphi TOPSIS for locating logistics centres in Vietnam [21], and ANP-TOPSIS for evaluating supply chain solutions [22]. Additionally, AHP has been used to enhance the performance of last-mile delivery service providers [15–17]. In the healthcare sector, researchers have evaluated internal supply chain performance using a DEMATEL-modified ANP approach [19].

As highlighted in previous literature, the effectiveness of MCDM methods in decision-making within logistics and supply chain management underscores the applicability of these techniques, ensuring that critical decisions are well-informed and based on a holistic evaluation. The literature review indicates that AHP has emerged as the predominant approach utilised across various contexts, including logistics and supply chain management [15,18,25]. Furthermore, TOPSIS, enhanced with fuzzy theory to address complexities and uncertainties in evaluation, has been adopted as a hybrid method [20,21,23].

The AHP-Fuzzy TOPSIS approach effectively incorporates stakeholder preferences into the decision-making process. Its justification stems from its capacity to manage complexity, uncertainty, and the diverse perspectives of stakeholders, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of alternatives [33]. This approach evaluates feasible alternatives for 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models by considering prioritised hospital logistics performance attributes. These metrics are assessed and ranked by logistics experts and managerial staff within hospitals, ensuring the selection of the most suitable model. Implementing the chosen model will enhance the management of hospital supply chains in the Thai context, ultimately improving enterprise competitiveness and service efficiency.

3. Methodology

In this research, an integrated MCDM approach was employed, combining the AHP with Fuzzy TOPSIS. This study is structured into three main stages, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Proposed research methodology.

Firstly, feasible supply chain management models for 3PL-operated SPD in Thai hospitals were identified as alternatives for decision-making. Simultaneously, decision criteria for evaluating and selecting the most suitable models were established through a comprehensive literature review, with a focus on performance attributes in hospital supply chain management, particularly resilience and economic factors. In this stage, both the proposed 3PL-operated SPD models and decision criteria were thoroughly examined and validated by seven experts, consisting of three academics and four professionals from the healthcare industry, each with over 10 years of experience in healthcare logistics and supply chain management. These experts were selected based on their accessibility, convenience, and relevance to the research topic [13,14].

The researcher conducted 1 h in-depth interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire that covered the supply chain management models and performance attributes derived from the literature review. Feasible alternatives that can be implemented in Thailand were added, while impractical options were removed. Additionally, performance attributes relevant to the Thai hospital context were incorporated as decision criteria. Both the decision criteria and alternatives were validated by the expert group.

The subsequent step involved the identification and prioritisation of hospital logistics performance attributes for assessing and selecting the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model. This study focused on deriving decision criteria from two primary dimensions of performance critical to supply chain operations managements: resilience and economic efficiency [34,35]. AHP was applied in this step to determine the significance of these criteria, utilising input from experts and relevant stakeholders in hospital supply chains. Following this, a hierarchical decision-making framework was established, comprising the set of decision criteria and sub-criteria, along with the proposed alternatives for 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models. Further details are provided in Section 5.

Finally, each 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model was evaluated based on the identified hospital logistics performance attributes. The ranking was calculated

using the Fuzzy TOPSIS method, incorporating the AHP-derived weights of each criterion. Ultimately, the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for implementation in Thai hospitals was selected based on the evaluation results. Detailed steps for the calculations in the AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS methods are provided in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, respectively.

3.1. The Calculation Steps of AHP

The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) is a widely utilised method for MCDM developed by Thomas L. Saaty in 1980 [36]. It is particularly effective for comparing decision components with varying attributes, relying on subjective judgments from decision-makers as input. AHP offers a systematic approach to transform qualitative performance assessments into quantifiable measurements, thereby facilitating the decision-making process [36,37]. The steps for calculating decision criteria weights in AHP are as follows:

Step 1: Problem definition and hierarchical structure construction—To effectively apply AHP, the initial step involves clearly defining the problem and objectives. This is achieved through discussions with experts and relevant stakeholders, which helps in establishing the decision criteria. This process decomposes the overarching problem into smaller, more manageable elements, enabling decision-makers to concentrate on a limited number of critical items. Once the problem is defined, a hierarchical structure is constructed. This structure typically features the goal at the top, followed by the criteria in the middle layer, and the various options or alternatives at the bottom. This hierarchical arrangement facilitates a clear understanding of the relationships among the different elements involved in the decision-making process [18,24,27].

Step 2: Criteria pairwise comparison—In this step, a pairwise comparison matrix is constructed to evaluate the relative importance of the decision criteria using a fundamental 9-point scale [36]. This matrix facilitates one-on-one comparisons between each pair of criteria, serving as a foundation for determining their relative weights.

The judgements obtained from these comparisons are instrumental in deriving the relative weights of the criteria. Each element a_{ij} (where $i, j = 1, \dots, n$) in the matrix signifies the relative weight of criterion i compared to criterion j , with $a_{ji} = 1/a_{ij}$. The results of all pairwise comparisons are summarised in an $n \times n$ reciprocal matrix, referred to as the pairwise comparison matrix (a_{ij}), where $a_{ii} = 1$ for all $i = 1, \dots, n$.

Step 3: Calculation of priority weight for criteria—The criteria are ranked in relation to the overall goal and the available options, with each criterion considered individually. The weights are derived from the pairwise comparison matrix established in the previous step, utilising the average of preference values provided by expert judgments. To ensure that the sum of all weights equals 1.00, normalisation principles are applied as follows:

(1) Normalisation of the pairwise comparison matrix: Each element of the matrix is divided by the sum of each column equal to 1.

(2) Calculation of eigenvalues and eigenvectors: The eigenvalues and eigenvectors for the normalised matrix are computed. The eigenvector (w) corresponding to the maximum eigenvalue (λ_{\max}) provides the relative weights for each criterion as follows:

$$Aw = \lambda_{\max} w \quad (1)$$

Step 4: Consistency test—The consistency test evaluates the degree of consistency within the decision matrix, which is crucial for ensuring the reliability of the decision-making process. This assessment involves comparing the calculated Consistency Index (CI) with a Random Index (RI), determined by Equation (2):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (2)$$

where the calculation of CI is performed by:

$$CI = \frac{(\lambda_{\max} - n)}{(n - 1)} \quad (3)$$

The resulting value is known as the Consistency Ratio (CR). If the CR is less than a predefined threshold (typically set as 0.1 or 10%), the judgments within the matrix are considered consistent and acceptable. Conversely, if the CR exceeds this threshold, this indicates inconsistencies, necessitating a re-evaluation of the decision matrix [36].

The weights derived from the AHP process serve as critical input used in the subsequent step, where the Fuzzy TOPSIS method is utilized. This method aimed to identify the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for hospitals in Thailand, integrating the prioritised decision criteria to facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of the alternatives.

3.2. The Calculation Steps of Fuzzy TOPSIS

The TOPSIS, introduced by Hwang and Yoon [38], is a widely recognised method in MCDM due to its simplicity and ease of use [27,39,40]. Its low mathematical complexity has facilitated its adoption across various fields [23,27], including supply chain management, to address MCDM problems [18,22,26,41].

TOPSIS is particularly effective for evaluating performance based on accurate values. It identifies the most favourable alternative by selecting the option that is closest to the positive ideal point (where the benefit criteria are maximised) and farthest from the negative ideal point (where the cost criteria are minimised) [39,42]. While TOPSIS is a straightforward weighting approach that often produces satisfactory results, it has limitations in decision-making scenarios where assigning precise performance ratings to alternatives proves challenging [23,27]. In these instances, fuzzy theory is integrated to manage the uncertainties inherent in subjective evaluations [20,33].

In this study, the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternatives were developed based on a comprehensive review of theories, some of which were newly proposed by experts in the field. The characteristics and advantages of these models are theoretically derived from the literature, making it difficult to evaluate their exact performance using precise numerical values. Consequently, this study employed fuzzy TOPSIS for model selection.

The calculation steps of fuzzy TOPSIS are as follows:

Step 1: Create a fuzzy decision matrix—A fuzzy decision matrix is developed by gathering linguistic variables from six experts. These experts express their preferences for each supply chain management model alternative using linguistic values outlined in Table 1. The linguistic values are subsequently converted into Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFN). Table 1 provides a list of the linguistic variables along with their corresponding TFNs, while Figure 4 illustrates the triangular membership function.

Table 1. Linguistic values and their fuzzy numbers.

Linguistic Value (x_{ijk})	Triangular Fuzzy Number ($a_{ijk}, b_{ijk}, c_{ijk}$)
Excellent	(7,9,9)
Good	(5,7,9)
Fair	(3,5,7)
Poor	(1,3,5)
Very Poor	(1,1,3)

Figure 4. Triangular membership function.

The fuzzy decision matrix for expert k , denoted as $\otimes D_k$, is formulated as shown in Equation (4). In this matrix, x_{ijk} represents the linguistic assessment of sub-criterion i (where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) for the supply chain management model alternative j (where $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) provided by expert k (where $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$). Each linguistic variable is characterised by three possible values, expressed as $x_{ijk} = (a_{ijk}, b_{ijk}, c_{ijk})$, which are detailed in Table 1.

$$\otimes D_k = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11k} & x_{21k} & \cdots & x_{n1k} \\ x_{12k} & x_{22k} & \cdots & x_{n2k} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ x_{1mk} & x_{2mk} & \cdots & x_{nmk} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Upon completing individual expert assessments for each sub-criterion associated with the respective alternatives, the collective expert scores are aggregated using the geometric mean, as presented in Equation (5). This aggregation results in a comprehensive evaluation, forming the basis for the aggregate fuzzy decision matrix, which is illustrated in Equation (6).

$$y_{ij} = \sqrt[k]{\prod_{k=1}^K x_{ijk}} \quad (5)$$

$$\otimes D = \begin{bmatrix} y_{11} & y_{21} & \cdots & y_{n1} \\ y_{12} & y_{22} & \cdots & y_{n2} \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \\ y_{1m} & y_{2m} & \cdots & y_{nm} \end{bmatrix}, \text{ where } y_{ij} = a_{ij}, b_{ij}, c_{ij} \quad (6)$$

Step 2: Normalise fuzzy decision matrix—To facilitate a comprehensive comparison of alternatives considering diverse criteria, a normalised fuzzy decision matrix, denoted as $\tilde{R} = [\tilde{r}_{ij}]$, is constructed. This normalisation scales all fuzzy evaluations to a common range of [0, 1] using Equations (7) and (8). The specific equation applied depends on whether the criterion is optimised for maximisation (benefit type) or minimisation (cost type).

$$\tilde{r}_{ij} = \left(\frac{a_{ij}}{c_i^*}, \frac{b_{ij}}{c_i^*}, \frac{c_{ij}}{c_i^*} \right) \text{ and } c_i^* = \max_j \{c_{ij}\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (7)$$

$$\tilde{r}_{ij} = \left(\frac{a_j^-}{c_{ij}}, \frac{a_j^-}{b_{ij}}, \frac{a_j^-}{a_{ij}} \right) \text{ and } a_j^- = \min_j \{a_{ij}\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (8)$$

Step 3: Derive the weighted normalised fuzzy decision matrix—Building upon the normalised fuzzy decision matrix $\tilde{R} = [\tilde{r}_{ij}]$, we proceed to incorporate the relative importance of each criterion. This is achieved by constructing the weighted normalised fuzzy decision matrix. As shown in Equation (9), this matrix is obtained by multiplying each element of \tilde{R} by the corresponding weight derived from the AHP analysis.

$$\tilde{V} = (\tilde{v}_{ij}), \text{ where } \tilde{v}_{ij} = \tilde{r}_{ij} \otimes \tilde{w}_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } j = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (9)$$

Step 4: Identify FPIS and FNIS for each alternative—This step involves identifying two crucial reference points used to evaluate the performance of each alternative. They are the Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS, A^*) and the Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS, A^-).

The FPIS is calculated using Equation (10) and represents the most desirable scenario for each criterion, characterised by the maximum fuzzy membership value observed across all of the alternatives under consideration. In contrast, the FNIS, determined by Equation (11), embodies the least favourable situation for each criterion, indicated by the minimum fuzzy membership value across all of the alternatives.

$$\tilde{A}_i^* = \max_{\forall j \in m} \{\tilde{v}_{ij}\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{10}$$

$$\tilde{A}_i^- = \min_{\forall j \in m} \{\tilde{v}_{ij}\}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{11}$$

Step 5: Calculate the Euclidian distance of each alternative from FPIS and FNIS—This step measures how closely each alternative aligns with the ideal solutions. The Euclidean distance from the FPIS (d^*) and FNIS (d^-) for each alternative is calculated using Equations (12) and (13), respectively.

$$d_j^* = \sum_{i=1}^n d(\tilde{v}_{ij}, \tilde{A}_i^*), i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{12}$$

$$d_j^- = \sum_{i=1}^n d(\tilde{v}_{ij}, \tilde{A}_i^-), i = 1, 2, \dots, n; j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{13}$$

The distance between two fuzzy numbers is denoted as $d(.,.)$ and is calculated using Equation (14).

$$d(\tilde{A}, \tilde{B}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} [(a_l - b_l)^2 + (a_m - b_m)^2 + (a_u - b_u)^2]} \tag{14}$$

Step 6: Calculate the closeness coefficient (CC_i) for each alternative—The closeness coefficient for each alternative is computed to measure how closely it aligns with the ideal solution. This coefficient is derived from the distances calculated in the previous step using Equation (15). The alternative with the highest closeness coefficient is deemed the best option, as it demonstrates the closest resemblance to the ideal solution.

$$CC_i = \frac{d_j^-}{d_j^* + d_j^-}, \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, m \tag{15}$$

4. The Alternatives for 3PL-Operated SPD Supply Chain Management Models

The alternatives for 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models feasible for implementation in Thai hospitals were investigated through a review of relevant literature and empirical adoption aspects. These supply chain models were then reviewed and validated by experts in hospital logistics and supply chain management. Seven experts, selected based on accessibility and convenience, were involved in this process. The expert panel consisted of:

- Two experts from a 3PL provider firm: One is a top executive with 12 years of experience, and the other is a middle-level manager with 10 years of experience.
- Two experts from a large tertiary private hospital: One is an executive, and the other is a middle-level manager.
- Three academicians specialising in healthcare logistics and supply chain management.

Given their extensive experience, with each expert having over 10 years of experience in the healthcare sector, their insights and expertise were crucial for reviewing and

validating the initial proposed 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models for Thai hospitals.

In the review and validation process, each expert participated in an individual in-depth interview using semi-structured questionnaire, which included the feasible supply chain management models derived from the literature and empirical insights. The experts reviewed the proposed models (alternatives), providing feedback that could lead to potential revisions or refinements of the supply chain models, expanding beyond the alternatives provides by the researchers.

Based on the validation by the expert panel, four 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models were proposed as alternatives for the selection process. These alternatives are described as follows:

SC I: W-G (involving a centralised warehouse and Group Purchasing Organisation)—The 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model W-G represents a minimalistic supply chain structure that include two main SPD functions: a centralised warehouse (W) and a Group Purchasing Organisation (G). The centralised warehouse is responsible for overseeing the supply, processing, and distribution of medical consumables to every point of use (represented by the green line) within the hospital’s supply chain. Additionally, the Group Purchasing Organisation (GPO) unit negotiates the best procurement deals for all hospital members within the network, leveraging collective buying power to secure cost-effective supplies.

This simplified structure aims to streamline healthcare supply chain operations while generating significant income from both warehousing and purchasing activities. By centralising logistics and procurement functions, the model not only reduces redundancy but also optimises resource allocation across hospital networks. The structure of this proposed model is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. The 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model—SC I: W-G.

SC II: W-G-C (involving a centralised warehouse, GPO, and regional cross-docks)—The W-G-C supply chain management model extends the previous W-G structure by integrating regional cross-docks (C) into the network. This addition streamlines logistics processes, enhances logistical management across the supply chain, and reduce transportation costs [43–45].

Similar to the initial model, the GPO unit continues to negotiate optimal procurement deals for all hospitals within the network. The centralised warehouse is responsible for overseeing the supply, processing, and distribution of medical consumables to nearby hospitals and regional cross-docks (represented by the green line). For more distant hospitals, this model introduces the clustering of hospital members by adding regional cross-docks into the network [46]. These cross-docks facilitate partial processing and distribution to more distant hospitals (represented by the orange line), serving as intermediary points that improve the distribution flow.

Overall, the W-G-C model enhances cost efficiency through GPO negotiations, while also improving lead times and transportation costs compared to distribution solely from the centralised warehouse to all hospital members, particularly those located far from the central facilities [46–50]. The W-G-C supply chain management model is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model—SC II: W-G-C.

SC III: W-G-H (involving a centralised warehouse, GPO, and regional SPD hubs)—The W-G-H model modifies the SC II: W-G-C supply chain by replacing the regional cross-docks with regional SPD hubs. These hubs differ significantly from cross-docks in that they provide storage capabilities and are strategically located closer to hospitals than the centralised warehouse [12]. This proximity enhances flexibility in supporting hospitals, particularly in scenarios of unpredictable demand [51]. The model is designed to

increase efficiency by reducing stockouts and the urgency for emergency support, effectively addressing fluctuations in demand [52].

Similar to SC II: W-G-C, the GPO continues to negotiate procurement deals for all hospital members. The centralised warehouse is responsible for the supply, processing, and distribution of medical consumables to nearby hospitals and regional hubs (illustrated by the green line). The regional hubs provide additional storage, reducing transportation costs for deliveries from the centralised warehouse to the hubs and enhancing responsiveness for distant hospitals. In cases of emergency, distant hospitals can requisition supplies directly from the nearest regional hub (represented by the pink line).

Although this model offers advantages in terms of reduced transportation costs and improved responsiveness, it also poses challenges. The availability of stock at the regional hubs increases the risk of inventory management issues, such as excess inventory in some locations or stockouts in others, adding complexity to distribution management. The proposed SC III: W-G-H model is visualised in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model—SC III: W-G-H.

SC IV: W-G-H-C (involving a centralised warehouse, GPO, regional SPD hubs, and regional cross-docks)—The final proposed supply chain model, W-G-H-C, integrates a centralised warehouse (W), a unit of GPO (G), regional SPD hubs (H), and regional cross-docks (C). This model, as recommended by experts, is designed to maximise the benefits of negotiation power and supply efficiency.

The centralised warehouse oversees the supply, processing, and distribution of medical consumables throughout the entire network. The GPO unit enhances this model by negotiating the most competitive prices for items across all hospital members. Both regional cross-docks and regional SPD hubs are strategically located to optimise distribution for hospitals located at varying distances from the centralised facility.

This arrangement enables efficient reduction of transportation costs compared to relying solely on the centralised warehouse for distribution to distant hospitals. Furthermore, hospitals that are far from the centralised warehouse can receive their requisitions from the regional SPD hubs, effectively minimising lead times, transportation costs, and reducing risk of stockouts or emergency incidents. The W-G-H-C supply chain model is illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8. The 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model—SC IV: W-G-H-C.

All proposed 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models have been validated by experts and will serve as alternatives for selecting the most suitable structure for implementation in the hospital supply chain in Thailand.

5. Evaluation of the 3PL-Operated SPD Supply Chain Management Models for Thai Hospitals Using AHP-Fuzzy TOPSIS Approach

5.1. Developing the Hierarchical Decision-Making Structure

Within the framework of MCDM, a comprehensive set of criteria was established to evaluate the optimal 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for implementation in Thai hospital supply chains. This study focused on deriving decision criteria from two primary dimensions of performance critical to supply chain operations management: resilience and economic efficiency [34,35]. Resilience encompasses the reliability and responsiveness of supply chain operations, while economic efficiency emphasises cost optimisation and asset management effectiveness.

The identification of these criteria, which are associated with key performance attributes under these dimensions and specifically focus on SPD functions such as supply management, inventory management, and distribution activities, has been achieved

through an extensive literature review and validation by experts in hospital logistics and supply chain management.

The healthcare logistics performance attributes obtained from the literature review and expert approval, along with their descriptions, were organised and are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Healthcare logistics performance attributes.

Performance Perspective (Criteria)	Sub-Criteria	Description	Sources
Resilience	Bargaining Power of Buyers (hospitals) (RQ1)	Hospitals can enhance their bargaining power in the supply chain by collaborating with reputable suppliers in the healthcare industry. By leveraging these suppliers' strong reputations and commitment quality, hospitals can negotiate better terms, prices, and service levels.	Experts
	Supplier Management (RQ2)	Supplier management is an ongoing process that involves collaborating with selected suppliers within a supply chain network. This encompasses continuous efforts in supplier collaboration, development, and evaluation.	[53,54]
	Availability of Supplies (RQ3)	Supply availability refers to the ability of a supply chain to meet the demand for medical supplies and medications. This includes maintaining adequate stock levels to prevent shortages and ensuring high-quality service for both urgent and routine requests.	[19,54–57]
	Inventory Visibility (RQ4)	Inventory visibility refers to the ability to continuously monitor inventory levels throughout the supply chain network, encompassing both on-hand inventory and safety stock. This capability ensures real-time awareness of available stock quantities.	[58–60]
	Patient Safety (RQ5)	Efficient management of hospitals' supply chain enhances patient safety by minimising delays and errors in sourcing supplies. This ensures timely availability of medical resources, facilitating uninterrupted quality care.	[13,19,55,61]
	Delivery Accuracy (RQ6)	Delivery accuracy measures the effectiveness of the delivery process managed by expert providers, ensuring the correct delivery of items in terms of type, quantity, location, and inventory data. This aspect is crucial for maintaining supply chain integrity, as it guarantees timely and precise delivery to the intended destination.	[62,63]
Responsiveness (RS)	Procurement Cycle Time (RS1)	Procurement cycle time refers to the average duration from the initiation of a purchase request to the receipt of medical supplies. This timeframe encompasses all stages of the procurement process, including sourcing, supplier selection, purchasing, and delivery.	[53,56,57]
	Preparation Time (RS2)	Preparation time refers to the duration required to prepare medical supplies or medications for distribution to hospitals or healthcare facilities within the supply chain network. This period encompasses the time from receiving an order until the supplies or medications are ready for delivery.	[56,57,64]
	On-time Delivery (RS3)	On-time delivery refers to the commitment of deliver products fully and accurately within the agreed-upon timeframe, ensuring that the right items reach their destination as scheduled.	[19,56,57,60]
Economic	Purchasing Cost (CO1)	Purchasing cost refers to the expenses incurred specifically during the procurement process. This includes costs associated with sourcing suppliers, negotiating contracts, placing orders, and any other activities directly related to acquiring medical supplies or medications for hospitals in the supply chain network.	[53,65]
	Inventory Cost (CO2)	Inventory cost refers to the expenses associated with holding inventory in hospitals within the supply chain network. This includes costs such as storage, insurance, obsolescence, depreciation, and the cost of capital tied up in the inventory.	[63,65,66]
	Distribution Cost (CO3)	Distribution cost includes the expenses incurred in delivering medical supplies or medications from a centralised warehouse, regional cross-dock, or hub to various hospitals. This encompasses transportation, handling, packing, and other related costs associated with moving supplies to their destinations within the supply chain network.	[65,67]
Asset Management Efficiency and Productivity (AP)	Emergency Procurement (AP1)	Emergency procurement refers to the supply chain's swift response to urgent hospital demands. It involves rapidly sourcing medical supplies or medications to address unforeseen situations, such as patient surges or resource shortages.	Experts
	Utilisation Rate (AP2)	Utilisation rate measures the effectiveness with which hospital facilities in the supply chain network use inventory turnover for medical supplies or medications. It indicates whether warehouse storage is utilised optimally without exceeding capacity, ensuring efficient turnover and preventing overstocking or underutilisation.	[19,63]; Experts
	Delivery Frequency (AP3)	Delivery frequency refers to the rate at which shipments of medical supplies or medications are dispatched from a centralised warehouse, regional cross-dock, or hub to hospitals within the supply chain network. It ensures timely supply while preventing excessive inventory build-up or shortages.	[56,57,60]; Experts

These performance attributes serve as the criteria and sub-criteria for evaluating the proposed 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternatives outlined in Section 4. The hierarchical decision-making structure consists of five layers. The top layer represents the goal of evaluating the most appropriate 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for implementation in Thai hospitals. The second and third layers encompass the four main criteria categorised under two performance perspectives: resilience and economic efficiency. These criteria include reliability and quality (RQ), responsiveness (RS), cost (CO), and asset management efficiency and productivity (AP). In the fourth layer, the sub-criteria are detailed for each main criterion, totalling 15 performance attributes. The fifth layer includes the four alternative 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models: SC I: W-G, SC II: W-G-C, SC III: W-G-H, and SC IV: W-G-H-C. This hierarchical decision-making structure is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. The hierarchical decision-making structure for evaluating the most appropriate 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for implementation in Thai hospitals.

5.2. Application of AHP to Determine the Criteria and Sub-Criteria Weights

In this section, the AHP was applied to determine the weights of the criteria and sub-criteria outlined earlier for selecting the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for Thai hospitals. The AHP method allows a comparative evaluation of the four main criteria and 15 sub-criteria, enabling the assignment of relative weights that reflect their significance. Each criterion’s weight indicates the expected level of performance improvement from implementing the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model.

Six experts from six different hospitals in Thailand, each with at least 10 years of managerial experience in hospital supply chain management, participated in this evaluation. The experts individually compared each pair of criteria and sub-criteria pair using Saaty’s 9-point scale for relative importance judgments, which resulted in the creation of pairwise

comparison matrices. The geometric mean of these judgements was calculated and used to derive the relative weights for the criteria and sub-criteria.

To ensure the consistency of the evaluation, the consistency ratio (CR) was calculated for each matrix. An acceptable CR value, indicating consistency, must be lower than 0.1 (or 10%). If the CR exceeds this threshold, the matrix requires re-evaluation. Table 3 presents the consistency ratios for each criterion, while Table 4 illustrates the overall relative importance of the criteria and sub-criteria, alongside their geometric mean values.

Table 3. The consistency index (CI), random consistency index (RI), and consistency ratio (CR) of each criterion.

Criteria	<i>n</i>	λ_{max}	CI	RI	CR
Reliability and quality (RQ)	6	6.1113	0.0223	1.24	0.0180
Responsiveness (RS)	3	3.0028	0.0014	0.58	0.0024
Cost (CO)	3	3.0001	0.0000	0.58	0.0000
Asset management efficiency and productivity (AP)	3	3.0016	0.0008	0.58	0.0014

Table 4. The overall relative importance of the criteria and sub-criteria.

Performance Attributes	Criteria	Criteria Weight	Sub-Criteria	Local Weight	Global Weight	Rank
Resilience	Reliability and Quality (RQ)	0.3071	RQ1: Bargaining Power of Buyers (hospitals)	0.0500	0.0154	15
			RQ2: Supplier Management	0.0662	0.0203	14
			RQ3: Availability of Supplies	0.1514	0.0465	11
			RQ4: Inventory Visibility	0.1480	0.0455	13
			RQ5: Patient Safety	0.3732	0.1146	2
			RQ6: Delivery Accuracy	0.2111	0.0648	9
	Responsiveness (RS)	0.2849	RS1: Procurement Cycle Time	0.2829	0.0806	5
			RS2: Preparation Time	0.2684	0.0765	7
			RS3: On-time Delivery	0.4487	0.1279	1
Economic	Cost (CO)	0.1939	CO1: Purchasing Cost	0.2395	0.0464	12
			CO2: Inventory Cost	0.4008	0.0777	6
			CO3: Distribution Cost	0.3597	0.0697	8
	Asset management efficiency and productivity (AP)	0.2141	AP1: Emergency Procurement	0.3837	0.0821	4
			AP2: Utilisation Rate	0.3988	0.0854	3
			AP3: Delivery Frequency	0.2175	0.0466	10

CR = 0.0009.

The expert-weighted priorities reveal that “reliability and quality (RQ)” is the most critical factor in selecting a 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model for hospital, with a criterion weight 0.3071. This factor is closely followed by “responsiveness (RS)”, which focuses on delivery performance, holding a weight of 0.2849. “asset management efficiency and productivity (AP)” ranks third with a weight of 0.2141, while “cost (CO)” has the lowest weight at 0.1939, indicating its relatively lower importance in the decision-making.

Among the sub-criteria, the global weights derived from the AHP analysis rank the top five sub-criteria as follows: “on-time delivery (RS3)” (0.1279) > “patient safety (RQ5)” (0.1146) > “utilisation rate (AP2)” (0.0854) > “emergency procurement (AP1)” (0.0821) > “procurement cycle time (RS1)” (0.0806).

This ranking highlights the experts’ preference for a 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model that emphasises timely delivery, prioritises patient safety, minimises

delays and errors, optimises inventory and resource utilisation, and efficiently manages costs. As a result, the selection process should favour supply chain management models that excel in these critical areas. These validated relative weights were subsequently applied in the fuzzy TOPSIS process to determine the most suitable supply chain network model for implementation.

5.3. Implementation of Fuzzy TOPSIS to Select the Suitable 3PL-Operated SPD Supply Chain Management Model for Thai Hospitals

Building on the importance weights derived from the AHP analysis in Section 5.2, Fuzzy TOPSIS was integrated into the evaluation process for the supply chain management model alternatives. Fuzzy TOPSIS is particularly useful when handling the uncertainty and subjectivity inherent in various criteria and alternatives. The integration of fuzzy theory enhances decision-making by accounting for the vagueness and imprecision often present in expert judgements.

In this step, six hospital-based experts who participated in the AHP evaluation continued their involvement by providing ratings for the four supply chain management model alternatives. They individually selected linguistic values to assess the alternatives, which were then represented as triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) to capture the fuzziness in their assessments. These TFNs, which are commonly used in fuzzy logic to express uncertainty, are listed in Table 1, and represent the degree to which an alternative satisfies a specific criterion on a fuzzy scale.

After the experts provided their fuzzy ratings, the fuzzy values were averaged using the geometric mean, resulting in a comprehensive fuzzy decision matrix, presented in Table 5. This matrix aggregates the individual fuzzy judgements from the experts, synthesising their opinions into a single representation. By incorporating the fuzzy values into the decision matrix, the collective assessments reflect the group consensus, capturing the overall evaluation of the supply chain management model alternatives based on the predefined criteria and sub-criteria.

Table 5. The fuzzy decision matrix.

Sub-Criteria	SC I: W-G	SC II: W-G-C	SC III: W-G-H	SC IV: W-G-H-C
RQ1	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(3.5569, 5.5934, 7.6117)	(5.2884, 7.2994, 9.0000)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)
RQ2	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(3.5569, 5.5934, 7.6117)	(5.2884, 7.2994, 9.0000)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)
RQ3	(4.2172, 6.2573, 8.2768)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(5.5934, 7.6117, 9.0000)	(5.1369, 7.1966, 8.6308)
RQ4	(4.2172, 6.2573, 8.2768)	(2.9618, 5.1369, 7.1966)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)
RQ5	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(2.7200, 4.0442, 6.3381)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)	(4.2172, 6.2573, 8.2768)
RQ6	(2.8403, 3.6077, 5.9843)	(3.7141, 4.9898, 7.1867)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)	(4.5919, 6.6183, 8.6308)
RS1	(3.5569, 5.5934, 7.6117)	(3.5569, 5.5934, 7.6117)	(4.5919, 6.6183, 8.6308)	(4.2172, 6.2573, 8.2768)
RS2	(2.7200, 4.8568, 6.9014)	(2.7200, 4.8568, 6.9014)	(4.4604, 6.5250, 8.2768)	(3.5569, 5.5934, 7.6117)
RS3	(2.9618, 4.2774, 6.6092)	(2.0801, 2.9240, 5.2776)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(5.0000, 7.0000, 9.0000)
CO1	(2.9618, 5.1369, 7.1966)	(2.9618, 5.1369, 7.1966)	(4.0964, 6.1691, 7.9373)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)
CO2	(3.1326, 4.4604, 6.6092)	(3.2666, 5.2884, 7.2994)	(4.4604, 6.5250, 8.2768)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)
CO3	(2.9618, 5.1369, 7.1966)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)	(4.8568, 6.9014, 8.6308)	(3.8730, 5.9161, 7.9373)
AP1	(2.4662, 3.9283, 6.2488)	(2.6085, 4.0964, 6.2488)	(5.5934, 7.6117, 9.0000)	(4.5919, 6.6183, 8.6308)
AP2	(5.4332, 7.5044, 8.6308)	(4.3327, 6.4330, 7.9373)	(4.5919, 6.6183, 8.6308)	(4.0964, 6.1691, 7.9373)
AP3	(2.0536, 3.0041, 5.4258)	(2.6085, 4.9195, 6.8041)	(4.4604, 6.5250, 8.2768)	(4.7177, 6.8041, 8.2768)

Equations (7) and (8) were utilised to create the normalised fuzzy decision matrix. This normalisation step transforms the fuzzy values from the decision matrix into a standardised scale, with values ranging between 0 and 1. Normalisation allows for a consistent comparison of all criteria and sub criteria, ensuring that varying units of measurement do not skew the results.

Once the decision matrix was normalised, Equation (9) was applied to compute the fuzzy weight normalised matrix. This step involved multiplying each element in the normalised fuzzy decision matrix by the corresponding AHP weight assigned to each sub-criterion. By integrating the AHP weights, the relative importance of each sub-criterion was factored into the evaluation, ensuring that the criteria deemed most critical by the experts had a stronger influence on the final decision.

The resulting fuzzy weighted normalised matrix, presented in Table 6, serves as a key component in the Fuzzy TOPSIS process. It reflects the normalised and weighted ratings of each alternative across all criteria and sub-criteria, providing a balanced and objective assessment that incorporates both expert judgement and quantitative analysis.

Table 6. Weighted normalised fuzzy decision matrix.

Sub-Criteria	AHP Weight	SC I: W-G	SC II: W-G-C	SC III: W-G-H	SC IV: W-G-H-C
RQ1	0.0154	(0.0075, 0.0115, 0.0154)	(0.0072, 0.0113, 0.0154)	(0.0090, 0.0125, 0.0154)	(0.0086, 0.0123, 0.0154)
RQ2	0.0203	(0.0099, 0.0152, 0.0203)	(0.0095, 0.0149, 0.0203)	(0.0119, 0.0165, 0.0203)	(0.0114, 0.0163, 0.0203)
RQ3	0.0465	(0.0237, 0.0352, 0.0465)	(0.0227, 0.0347, 0.0465)	(0.0289, 0.0393, 0.0465)	(0.0277, 0.0388, 0.0465)
RQ4	0.0455	(0.0232, 0.0344, 0.0455)	(0.0187, 0.0324, 0.0455)	(0.0256, 0.0363, 0.0455)	(0.0256, 0.0363, 0.0455)
RQ5	0.1146	(0.0559, 0.0854, 0.1146)	(0.0492, 0.0731, 0.1146)	(0.0645, 0.0916, 0.1146)	(0.0584, 0.0867, 0.1146)
RQ6	0.0648	(0.0308, 0.0391, 0.0648)	(0.0335, 0.0450, 0.0648)	(0.0365, 0.0518, 0.0648)	(0.0345, 0.0497, 0.0648)
RS1	0.0806	(0.0377, 0.0592, 0.0806)	(0.0377, 0.0592, 0.0806)	(0.0429, 0.0618, 0.0806)	(0.0411, 0.0609, 0.0806)
RS2	0.0765	(0.0301, 0.0538, 0.0765)	(0.0301, 0.0538, 0.0765)	(0.0412, 0.0603, 0.0765)	(0.0357, 0.0562, 0.0765)
RS3	0.1279	(0.0573, 0.0827, 0.1279)	(0.0504, 0.0708, 0.1279)	(0.0624, 0.0953, 0.1279)	(0.0710, 0.0994, 0.1279)
CO1	0.0464	(0.0191, 0.0331, 0.0464)	(0.0191, 0.0331, 0.0464)	(0.0240, 0.0361, 0.0464)	(0.0227, 0.0346, 0.0464)
CO2	0.0777	(0.0368, 0.0524, 0.0777)	(0.0348, 0.0563, 0.0777)	(0.0419, 0.0613, 0.0777)	(0.0379, 0.0579, 0.0777)
CO3	0.0697	(0.0287, 0.0498, 0.0697)	(0.0340, 0.0520, 0.0697)	(0.0392, 0.0558, 0.0697)	(0.0340, 0.0520, 0.0697)
AP1	0.0821	(0.0324, 0.0516, 0.0821)	(0.0343, 0.0538, 0.0821)	(0.0511, 0.0695, 0.0821)	(0.0437, 0.0630, 0.0821)
AP2	0.0854	(0.0537, 0.0742, 0.0854)	(0.0466, 0.0692, 0.0854)	(0.0454, 0.0655, 0.0854)	(0.0441, 0.0664, 0.0854)
AP3	0.0466	(0.0176, 0.0258, 0.0466)	(0.0178, 0.0337, 0.0466)	(0.0251, 0.0367, 0.0466)	(0.0265, 0.0383, 0.0466)

Following the creation of the fuzzy weighted normalised matrix, Equations (10) and (11) were employed to establish the FPIS (A^*) and FNIS (A^-). The FPIS represents the best possible scenario, where all criteria are met at their highest levels, while the FNIS reflects the worst-case scenario, where all criteria are at their lowest levels. These ideal solutions serve as reference points for evaluating the performance of each alternative in the decision-making process.

The outcomes of these distance calculations, which indicate the relative performance of each 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternative, are detailed in Table 7.

As presented in Table 7, the alternative SCIII: W-G-H demonstrates the closest distance to the positive ideal solution across most hospital logistics performance attributes or sub-criteria, outperforming the other alternatives. Similarly, SC III also shows the farthest distance from the negative ideal solution for almost all sub-criteria, indicating that this model is the most favourable option for the majority of performance attributes when compared to the other three models.

Table 7. Distances of alternatives from FPIS and FNIS.

Sub-Criteria	Distance from FPIS				Distance from FNIS			
	SC I: W-G	SC II: W-G-C	SC III: W-G-H	SC IV: W-G-H-C	SC I: W-G	SC II: W-G-C	SC III: W-G-H	SC IV: W-G-H-C
RQ1	0.0051	0.0053	0.0040	0.0043	0.0053	0.0053	0.0057	0.0056
RQ2	0.0067	0.0070	0.0053	0.0056	0.0071	0.0070	0.0076	0.0075
RQ3	0.0147	0.0154	0.0110	0.0117	0.0155	0.0154	0.0171	0.0168
RQ4	0.0144	0.0172	0.0126	0.0126	0.0181	0.0174	0.0189	0.0189
RQ5	0.0378	0.0447	0.0318	0.0363	0.0434	0.0402	0.0459	0.0439
RQ6	0.0247	0.0214	0.0180	0.0196	0.0202	0.0214	0.0234	0.0226
RS1	0.0277	0.0277	0.0243	0.0255	0.0277	0.0277	0.0286	0.0283
RS2	0.0298	0.0298	0.0224	0.0263	0.0300	0.0300	0.0326	0.0309
RS3	0.0484	0.0555	0.0256	0.0367	0.0486	0.0463	0.0619	0.0543
CO1	0.0175	0.0175	0.0143	0.0153	0.0177	0.0177	0.0188	0.0183
CO2	0.0277	0.0277	0.0228	0.0257	0.0268	0.0277	0.0294	0.0282
CO3	0.0263	0.0230	0.0194	0.0230	0.0266	0.0274	0.0290	0.0274
AP1	0.0337	0.0321	0.0194	0.0248	0.0308	0.0313	0.0374	0.0343
AP2	0.0194	0.0243	0.0237	0.0282	0.0322	0.0300	0.0298	0.0282
AP3	0.0206	0.0182	0.0136	0.0125	0.0174	0.0191	0.0205	0.0212

However, SC III does not perform best for two specific performance attributes under the asset management efficiency and productivity criteria: utilisation rate (AP2) and delivery frequency (AP3).

For AP2 (utilisation rate), the best alternative is SC I: W-G, as this model comprises only one inventory storage facility at the central hospital warehouse. This centralised management of inventory allows for optimal utilisation, reducing the risk of overstocking or underutilisation across other hospital facilities. However, this model presents a potential risk of exceeding capacity at the central warehouse due to the concentration of all inventory at a single location.

For AP3 (delivery frequency), the optimal model is one that includes additional hospital facilities at regional locations, such as regional SPD hubs and cross-docks, which is best represented by SC IV: W-G-H-C. This model ensures timely supply to hospital members while avoiding excessive inventory build-up or shortages. Hospitals far from the central warehouse can receive their requisitions from nearby regional facilities, enhancing delivery efficiency without overburdening the central warehouse.

Thus, while SC III: W-G-H emerges as the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model overall, SC I and SC IV may offer advantages in certain specific areas, such as utilisation rate and delivery frequency, respectively.

Subsequently, the positive distance (d^*) from the FPIS and the negative distance (d^-) from the FNIS were calculated for each alternative. These distances provide valuable insights into how closely each supply chain model alternative aligns with the ideal solution and how far they are from the negative ideal solution.

The distance measures were used to compute the closeness coefficient (CC) for each alternative, which represents the degree of closeness to the ideal solution. The CC was determined using Equation (15). The CC values provide a numerical ranking of each alternative, with higher values indicating a better fit with the ideal solution. The CC values and the corresponding ranking of the evaluated 3PL-operated supply chain management model alternatives are summarised in Table 8.

Table 8. Closeness coefficient (CC) and ranking of alternatives.

Alternative	SC I: W-G	SC II: W-G-C	SC III: W-G-H	SC IV: W-G-H-C
d^*	0.3544	0.3667	0.2683	0.3081
d^-	0.3676	0.3639	0.4065	0.3863
Closeness coefficient (CC)	0.5091	0.4981	0.6025	0.5563
Rank of alternative	3	4	1	2

As depicted in Table 8, the rankings based on the closeness coefficients (CC) for the 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternatives are in the following order: SC III: W-G-H > SC IV: W-G-H-C > SC I: W-G > SC II: W-G-C. It is evident that SC III: W-G-H emerges as the most suitable supply chain management model for implementation in Thai hospitals, with the highest closeness coefficient (CC) of 0.6025. This model integrates regional SPD hubs, which are strategically positioned closer to hospitals than the centralised warehouse, providing greater flexibility in responding to periods of unpredictable demand. This model ensures timely delivery while maintaining sufficient inventory levels, making it a highly responsive and adaptable network compared to the other alternatives.

6. Discussion and Practical Implications

6.1. Discussion of the Obtained Results and Research Contributions

Hospitals have increasingly encountered pressure to enhance their operational efficiency by focusing on core healthcare functions while outsourcing non-core activities, such as supply processing distribution (SPD), to proficient logistics entities like 3PL providers [1]. Effective management of non-healthcare operations by logistics professionals can facilitate timely and cost-effective delivery of supplies to healthcare institutions, ultimately improving responsiveness and ensuring patient safety.

This research contributes significantly to the field by introducing an innovative supply chain management model tailored specifically for the hospital industry in Thailand. While the concept of integrating 3PLs into hospital logistics is common in sectors such as retail [15,16], this study pioneers its application within the healthcare context.

This study advocates for the integration of novel logistics infrastructures—including centralised warehouses, group purchasing organisations, cross-docks, and regional SPD hubs—into the hospital supply chain framework. By amalgamating these components with logistics expertise, the research produces four potential 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternatives. These alternatives encompass essential characteristics necessary for efficient hospital supply chain management, such as competitive pricing negotiation, effective inventory turnover management, responsiveness, and support for urgent demands. This work also positions these models within a MCDM framework, enabling a structured approach to identifying the most appropriate model for enhancing the hospital supply chain in Thailand.

In evaluating the optimal alternative, this study highlights two critical performance attributes: resilience and economic efficiency, both of which are vital in managing supply chain operations. Through an extensive literature review and expert consultation, this research identifies four primary hospital performance attributes along with 15 sub-criteria. The AHP results revealed that responsiveness ranks as the most important criterion, closely followed by reliability and quality. This underscores the critical need for timely and high-quality patient care in the healthcare sector. Notably, financial cost ranks lowest, reflecting a prioritisation of patient welfare over cost considerations in high-stakes healthcare scenarios. Key sub-criteria include on-time delivery, patient safety, utilisation rates, and emergency procurement—all essential for ensuring the availability of medical supplies and medications. These findings align with previous research in healthcare supply chain management [13,14,19,50,65].

To identify the most suitable 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management models for implementation in Thai hospitals, this study employed the Fuzzy TOPSIS method. The findings indicate that the model with the highest closeness coefficient (CC) of 0.6025 is SC III: W-G-H, which features a centralised warehouse to enhance negotiation power, a group purchasing organisation (GPO), for cost efficiency, and regional SPD hubs to facilitate efficient inventory management and rapid responses to demand fluctuations or emergencies. However, SC IV: W-G-H-C, which ranks second with a CC of 0.5563, also demonstrates significant potential. These approaches align with various research initiatives in the healthcare context. For instance, the integration of logistics facilities into the healthcare supply chain during the COVID-19 pandemic illustrated the effectiveness of healthcare unit hubs in managing home isolation by efficiently distributing medications and medical supplies to patients [50]. Similarly, optimised distribution planning in healthcare can enhance service efficiency and reduce costs [46].

Nonetheless, this study acknowledges that the addition of inventory at multiple logistics facilities may complicate inventory management, underscoring the need for cautious implementation that aligns with hospital contexts and the readiness of 3PL providers. Furthermore, it recognises that ideal logistics frameworks may encounter obstacles in the complex, high-risk healthcare sector, which is often characterised by unpredictability [1]. The diverse characteristics of hospitals in Thailand—including variations in administration, care levels, and bed capacities—may require customised supply chain management models to address these complexities.

6.2. Practical Implications

From a managerial perspective, this study suggests that hospital administrators can utilise the proposed MCDM methodology to prioritise relevant criteria and sub-criteria specific to their organisations. This approach empowers decision-makers to reassess their optimal supply chain management models based on tailored weighted sets that meet their unique operational needs [25,27].

Practically, hospitals can implement the novel supply chain management model in several key ways:

- (1) Customised supply chain strategies: Hospitals should conduct thorough assessments of their current supply chain frameworks, considering the unique characteristics of their operations, such as patient volume, types of services offered, and existing partnerships. By applying the MCDM methodology, hospital administrators can develop customised supply chain strategies that prioritise responsiveness, reliability, and quality of service, ensuring that they align with the specific needs of their patient populations.
- (2) Integration of logistics infrastructures: This study recommends the incorporation of logistics infrastructures—such as centralised warehouses, group purchasing organisations (GPO), cross-docks, and regional SPD hubs—into the hospital supply chain. Hospitals can collaborate with 3PL providers to establish these infrastructures, which will enhance negotiation power, streamline inventory management, and facilitate rapid responses to fluctuations in demand. This strategic integration will not only optimise operational efficiency but also improve the overall patient experience through timely access to necessary medical supplies.
- (3) Collaboration with 3PL providers: By recognising the potential of 3PLs to enhance supply chain efficiency, hospitals can forge strategic partnerships with logistics firms that possess the necessary expertise in managing SPD functions. This collaboration will enable hospitals to leverage 3PL capabilities in inventory management, procurement, and distribution, thereby freeing up internal resources to focus on core healthcare services. Moreover, hospitals should establish clear communication channels with their 3PL partners to ensure alignment of goals and to facilitate prompt responses to urgent healthcare demands.

- (4) **Training and development:** Implementing the proposed supply chain management model may require staff training and development to ensure that hospital personnel are well-equipped to manage new logistics processes and technologies. Hospitals should invest in continuous education programs that focus on supply chain management principles, technology utilisation, and effective collaboration with logistics partners. This investment will enhance staff competencies [15], ultimately leading to improved operational performance and patient outcomes.
- (5) **Monitoring and evaluation:** Hospitals should establish key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor the effectiveness of the implemented supply chain management model. Regular evaluation of these KPIs will provide insights into operational efficiencies, responsiveness, and cost-effectiveness, allowing for ongoing adjustments to the supply chain strategy. This data-driven approach will enable hospitals to remain agile and responsive to changes in the healthcare landscape, ensuring sustained improvements in service delivery.
- (6) **Emphasising patient-centred care:** The study highlights the importance of prioritising patient well-being over financial considerations in healthcare scenarios. Hospitals should ensure that their supply chain strategies are aligned with a patient-centred approach, focusing on delivering high-quality care and improving patient safety [13,14,19]. By adopting this perspective, hospitals can enhance their reputation, build trust within their communities, and ultimately contribute to better health outcomes.

In conclusion, this research underscores the potential for 3PLs to enhance supply chain efficiency and fulfil hospital customer expectations, significantly contributing to the essential objective of saving lives. By applying the proposed supply chain management model, hospitals can navigate the complexities of modern healthcare logistics, ultimately achieving improved operational performance and enhanced patient care.

7. Conclusions

This research introduced a novel supply chain management model designed to transform hospital supply chains in Thailand, with a specific focus on integrating 3PL providers to optimise SPD functions. This study identified four potential 3PL-operated SPD supply chain management model alternatives, considering critical attributes such as negotiation power, inventory management efficiency, responsiveness, and cost-effectiveness. Utilising the AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS methodologies, these alternatives were evaluated against various criteria and sub-criteria relevant to hospital logistics performance. The findings revealed that the SC III: W-G-H model is the most suitable option, which incorporates a centralised warehouse to strengthen negotiation power, a GPO to enhance cost efficiency, and regional SPD hubs to facilitate effective inventory management and quick responses to demand fluctuations or emergencies. However, this study also recognises that the inclusion of additional logistics facilities, such as regional hubs or cross-docks, may complicate inventory management, which requires careful consideration during implementation.

The insights gained from this research provide valuable guidance for hospital decision-makers in Thailand, emphasising the need for customised supply chain management models that reflect the unique characteristics and requirements of individual hospitals. The proposed MCDM methodology serves as a systematic framework that allows decision-makers to prioritise relevant criteria and sub-criteria based on their organisational needs, thereby facilitating the selection of the optimal supply chain management model. Overall, this study illustrates the potential of 3PLs to enhance supply chain efficiency within the healthcare sector, ultimately contributing to improved patient care and safety. Nevertheless, it also underscores the inherent complexities and challenges associated with healthcare logistics, highlighting the need for meticulous planning and execution of supply chain strategies in this critical industry.

Despite the valuable insights gained from this study, several limitations must be acknowledged:

- **Sample size and expert selection:** This study relied on insights from six experts across different hospitals in Thailand, which may limit the diversity of perspectives and experiences related to healthcare logistics. Given the constraints of budget and time, future research should aim to incorporate a larger and more diverse sample of experts from a range of healthcare facilities—such as public, private, urban, and rural institutions—to obtain a broader spectrum of insights.
- **Geographical focus:** The emphasis on Thai hospitals may restrict the applicability of the findings to other healthcare systems with different contexts and challenges. Future studies could conduct comparative analyses across multiple countries or regions. This would not only validate the findings but also provide insights into how various factors influence supply chain management across different healthcare settings.

By proactively addressing these limitations and implementing mitigation strategies, future research can enhance the validity and applicability of these findings in the field of healthcare supply chain management, ultimately leading to more effective logistics operations in hospitals.

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